

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

O'tkir Eshaliyev Soatmurodovich

Teacher of the Department of Technological Education of Termiz State University.
Uzbekistan e-mail address: utkireshaliyev70@gmail.com

Abstract:

This article answers the questions: What is information technology? What does an information society look like? What is their interdependence?

Key words: Information, information, technology, information technology, technical means, information system, supply, information society, electrical, mechanical, electronic, telecommunications, computer, equipment, information, communications.

Wide development of information and communication technologies is a global trend of world development in the next decades. In today's rapidly developing world, information and communication technologies are the main factor driving economic development, they help attract investments to the country, create new jobs, introduce advanced technologies in production and management, market participants. It is becoming a means of reducing costs in the exchange of information and negotiations. Taking this into account, the Government of Uzbekistan considers this direction as a strategic priority for economic development and raising the standard of living of the population. The success of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan creates the need to fundamentally change the attitude to the provision of information in society. In social production, information is turning from an auxiliary and secondary factor into the main factor affecting the economy, defense and politics. In addition, it is considered a direct factor of economic development, which requires the involvement of a significant part of material resources. As a result of these features, information is becoming the information power or information resources of the socio-economic sphere. Therefore, in the development of the socio-economic sphere, the problems of rational formation of the national information system and their use are of great importance. Formation of the national information system, mass introduction and use of modern information technologies, computer equipment and telecommunication tools in all spheres of economy and social life, more complete satisfaction of the growing demands and needs for information, access to the world information community and enjoyment of world information resources. based on the need to create favorable conditions for expansion, the decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 21, 2012, that the measures for the wider introduction of modern information and communication technologies are appropriate. Based on this decision, at the meeting of the coordinating council for the development of computerization and information and communication technologies held in the Cabinet of Ministers, the implementation of the program for the wider introduction and development of modern information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan in 2012-2014 was approved. The schedule for the provision was approved. Also, the composition of the working group on the development of the mechanism and criteria for the implementation of information systems and the effectiveness of the use of the Internet in state bodies was approved, and its main tasks were determined. The rapid development of the economy cannot be imagined without information technologies. As a proof of this, the creation of a national system of informatization, mass introduction of modern information technologies, computer equipment and telecommunication tools in all spheres of economy and social life, a favorable condition for more

fully meeting the growing information needs of citizens, entering the world information society, and expanding the enjoyment of world information resources - sharoitlar yaratilib is getting married. Formation of the market mechanism in the economy, creation of the necessary conditions for the operation of the main subjects of the market - producers and consumers, requires the information environment for entrepreneurs to be compatible with these mechanisms. In this environment, it is necessary to provide information support to the subjects of the market mechanism at all stages of products, services and consumption, as well as all areas of their activity. The entrepreneur is informed about other entrepreneurs, the expected consumers of food, components and technologies, prices, the state of the product and capital market, the situation in the life of businessmen in terms of the general economic situation not only in their country, but in the whole world. information about the situation, about the long-term directions of the prospects and consequences of the economy, science and technology development, about the legal conditions of business management, etc. is very necessary. Therefore, an important task of the formation of the information infrastructure of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to create the best conditions for entrepreneurs to receive information. This information is called Business Information or Business Information in the world. The complexity of the problem is determined by the fact that it is characterized by a large variety of connections and must be solved in the conditions of changing the economic mechanism and its structure. Another important aspect of the issue is that the relationship between the state and economic entities is changing radically. The opportunities of your state to fully influence the information market are not sufficient. As a result, a number of deficiencies in the information and communication infrastructure of the Republic of Uzbekistan make obtaining information a problem for participation in the market and social relations. In this case, solving the problem requires non-standard approaches. A complete solution to this problem requires global information to be carried out in harmony with the dynamics of the world.

List of used literature

1. Karimov I.A. World financial and economic crisis, ways and measures to eliminate it in the conditions of Uzbekistan. T.: Uzbekistan, 2009, 56 p.
2. Ivasenko A. G. Information technology and economic management: Teaching methods. A. G. Ivasenko, A. Yu. Gridasov, V. A. Pavlinko. - M.: KNORUS, 2005. str. 20-68.
3. U.S. Eshaliyev. "THE FUTURE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE TEACHER COMPETENCE OF NURTURING THE TECHNOLOGY IMPROVEMENT" ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 2, Feb., 2022
4. U.S. Eshaliyev. "Professional Competence of a Computer Science Teacher Diagnostic Methodology" Vol. 02 Issue 04 (2022):EJINE
5. U.S. Eshaliyev. "Preparing Future Computer Science Teachers to Work with Gifted Students." Computer-Based Implementation Technology" EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF LIFE SAFETY AND STABILITY (EJLSS) ISSN 2660-9630 www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org Volume 9, 2021
6. O.S. Eshaliyev. "Methodology for diagnosing the professional knowledge of a computer science teacher" Society and innovations Journal home page: <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/index> Received in revised form 20 June 2022 Accepted 25 July 2022 Available online 15 August 2022

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-7

7. U.S. Eshaliyev. "Theoretical Foundations of Improving the Technology of Training the Competence of the Future Informatics Teacher" American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research (AJSHR). October, Vol. 3 No. 10 (2022): AJSHR.

8. O.S. Eshaliyev. "SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE IT TEACHER" Magazine for teachers. Issue 34 2-set_ July_ 2022.

9. U.S. Eshaliyev. "Theoretical Foundations of Improving the Technology of Training the Competence of the Future Informatics Teacher" AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN RESEARCH. ISSN: 2690-9626 Vol. 3, No. 10, 2022.

10. U.S. Eshaliyev. "The Advantage of Using Multimedia Electronic Teaching-Methodical Complexes in Forming the Intellectual Competence of the Listener" International Journal of Development and Public Policy. ISSN: 2690-9626 Vol. 3, No. 10, 2022

